

north american
academic research

Research

Research on Computer Simulation of the Stitch Forming Jacquard Warp-Knitted Fabric

Jalal Ahmed¹, Afshan Zareen², MD. Mamunur Rahman¹, Farzana Akter², Shamima Sarker³, Moyinul Islam⁴, Rasnatun Ferdous⁵, Md Mehedi Hasan Rubel^{1, *}

¹ School of Textile Science & Engineering, Wuhan Textile University, Wuhan, China.

² College of Textile Engineering, Donghua University, Shanghai, China.

³ Department of Textile Engineering, Green University of Bangladesh, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

⁴ School of Material Science & Engineering, Huazhong University of Science & Technology, Wuhan, China.

⁵ Department of Textile Engineering, City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

***Corresponding Author**

Accepted : 16 June, 2019 Published online :17 June, 2019

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3247962>

Abstract: Based on a supplementary study on jacquard standards warp knitting technology and their construction, this study offers the modern simulation design model of computer-aided design (CAD) to fabricate stitch forming jacquard warp-knitted fabric highly methodical. In particular, the application of knitting CAD technology develops it more expedient to design and manufacture fabric for textile industry it brings huge social and economic advantage. According to the research of warp knitting technology is the basic of computer graphics and other programming technical tools as like as VC++6.0, integrative is a key to complete the study. At first, the thesis establishes the process of fabric simulation model and expansion of stitch forming jacquard warp knitted fabric in essence. After that, the research analyses the structure and improvement of the stitch forming jacquard warp knitted fabric, acquire the appearance of fabric looks as well as affects the parameters of its. The research is correlated with mathematical models and technical methods for simulation of this type of fabric. Finally, the research designs the software (CAD) which is applied to simulate the stitch forming jacquard warp knitted fabric, and also develop with the computer programming tool VC++6.0. Comprehend the simulation this kind of fabric construction and gets final design with some fabric effect.

Keywords: Warp-Knitted fabric, CAD Technology, Stitch forming Jacquard, Simulation Model.

1. Introduction

This paper first briefly introduces the application of computer simulation technology for

fabrics and the improvement of loop jacquard warp knitted fabric, then elaborates the importance of the studies, introduces the associated research and improvement popularity at domestic and overseas and eventually lists the studies targets and contents of the challenge inside the light of the actual situation of the research.

In recent years, with the continuous development and development of computer application technology, computer powerful mathematical calculation and snap shots processing capability has been extensively utilized in industry. The earliest software of CAD technology in foreign nations commenced in 1960s.

At that point, IBM Corporation of America first advanced an automated system of weaving system which can update manual design. It can be said that the application of computer simulation technology for fabrics cannot simplest improve the characteristic integration and perfection of cylinder fabric CAD system, however also have a very essential sensible significance within the process of fabric manufacturing. The research goal of this paper is to analyze the technological shape of loop jacquard warp knitted fabrics thoroughly and meticulously, to gain a complete hold close of the advent and fashion of such fabric, to examine the associated simulation mathematical version of this form of fabric, establish the computer simulation mathematical model of loop jacquard warp knitted fabrics mixed with its own relevant influencing factors and to make the corresponding smooth.

2. Structure Analysis of Jacquard

Loop-forming jacquard warp knitted fabric have extraordinary patterns that are especially due to the rich adjustments within the structure of jacquard fabric. The transverse displacement of the lower back of the needle varies in importance by means of the usage of the jacquard guide needle to perform the deviation motion of the jacquard guide needle in step with the pattern requirement even as making the primary organizational movement. The transverse displacement of the jacquard guide needle can be expressed by the following formula:

U-jacquard yarn guide needle transverse displacement = U-jacquard yarn guide needle basic transverse displacement + U-jacquard yarn guide needle offset

Among them, the fundamental transverse displacement of jacquard guide needle could be decided by way of the jacquard needle choice technology. The jacquard guide needle will produce a needle offset. The principle of basic jacquard is shown in fig 1.

Figure 1. Principle of basic jacquard

2.1. Three-Needle Technique

According to the design requirements, the basic cushion yarn with three needles technology can also choose the 0-1/2-1// form of the open 1X1 warp flat weave. From figure 2, it can be seen that the jacquard pattern effect formed by three-needle technique is more comprehensive.

Figure 2. Motion chart of three-needle technology cushion yarn

2.2. Stitch through Flat Ground

(1) GB2/ 1-2/1-0// Full threaded

(2) GB2/ 1-2/1-0// Full threaded,

GB3/ 1-0/1-2/1-2/1-0// full threaded

Figure 3. Plane stitch

This sort of structure for fabric substrates can be used as co-directional or opposite cushioning yarns for the next two bars. As shown in fig (3).

2.3. Satin Weave

The elastic jacquard is used to make a needle lining of 1-1/0-0//, the fabric will produce elasticity in the longitudinal direction, as shown in fig 4.

Figure 4. Plane stitch

2.4. Mathematical Description of Transforming

δ _____ Volume weight of yarn (g/cm^3);

h _____ twist distance (mm);

N_t _____ yarn count;

β _____ twist angle;

d _____ Yarn diameter (mm);

A _____ The rotation angle of the block model;

T_{tex} _____ twist of yarn (twist /1cm);

X _____ length of block model;

Y _____ The width of the block model.

Here,

$$d = 0.03667 \sqrt{\frac{N_t}{\delta}} \quad (1)$$

$$T_g \beta = T_{\text{tex}} / 892 \sqrt{\frac{N_t}{\delta}} \quad (2)$$

$$h = 100 / T_{\text{tex}} \quad (3)$$

$$a = 90 - \beta \quad (4)$$

$$X = d / \sin \beta \quad (5)$$

$$Y = h \quad (6)$$

$$a = 90 - \text{tg}^{-1} \left(T_{\text{tex}} / 892 \sqrt{\frac{N_l}{\delta}} \right)$$

$$X = 0.03667 \sqrt{\frac{N_l}{\delta}} / \sin \left(\text{tg}^{-1} \left(T_{\text{tex}} / 892 \sqrt{\frac{N_l}{\delta}} \right) \right); Y = 100 / T_{\text{tex}}$$

3. Yarn Simulation Model Style

The main factors affecting the computer simulation of yarn appearance are concentrated on the front, namely, yarn roving, yarn color, yarn twist, yarn strength, raw fabric, yarn hairiness etc. Yarn color varies greatly due to yarn twist, strand number, fiber thickness and other external factors such as tension, light and so on. Fig (5) is a scanning image of a yarn pattern.

Figure 5. Yarn Pattern Scanning Chart

3.1. Weft-Inserting Warp-Knitted Loop Model

The warp knitted yarn is completely bendable, but the weft insertion yarn is not smooth to bend due to its excessive stiffness. When warp putting and braiding are used as back side weaves, weft insertion yarns are held together with them as shown in fig (6) respectively.

Figure 6. Weft-inserting warp-knitted loop model

3.2. Main Interface Table of Design of System

Table 1. Sub-menu Commands, Shortcuts and Function Descriptions of the File menu

Menu Comm and	Hot key	Function description
---------------------	------------	----------------------

New	Ctrl+N	Create a new Jacquard pattern file
Turn on	Ctrl+O	Open an existing Jacquard pattern file
Save	Ctrl+S	Save the current Jacquard pattern file
Save as	Ctrl+A	Save the current Jacquard pattern file with a new file name
Recent file	Ctrl+L	Open current pattern file
Drop out	Ctrl+X	Exit fabric pattern simulation system

3.3. Geometric Model of Weft-Inserting Loop Structure

Here's P1, P2,... P4 is an important parameter point on the loop, which is likewise represented through 'X' and 'Y'. The relationship among the range of parameters inside the loop model at the left stop of weft insertion is as follows:

$$P1.x=(k+1/6)(b1c, P1 y)=(j-1/3)$$

$$P2.x=(k+1/3)(b1c, P2 y)=(j-1/5)$$

$$P3.x=(k+1/3)(b1c, P3y)=(j+1/5)$$

$$P4.x=k+1/6*b1c, P1.y=j+1/3$$

Among them, the actual size ratio $BLC = WPC/$ computer, J and K are the values of cutting-edge horizontal and vertical respectively and point P5 and P4 coincide. We assemble the geometric version of weft-inserting loop structure as shown in Fig 7.

Figure 7. Geometric model of weft-inserting loop

4. System Software Interface Example & Design Making

According to the design of the machine within the previous sections and the adoption of HZCAD and VC++ programming technology, we have advanced the simulation device JDS1.0 for loop jacquard warp knitted fabrics. Open the "HZCAD" software, there are command execution buttons at the person login window, one is the "Log on System" button

Figure 10. Simulation effect

4.3. Main Process Parameters

Organization: GB2: 2-3/2-1/1-0/1-2//, Needle selection technique: Closed three-needle pattern cycle: 2*1, Yarn colour: JB1 (red), GB2 (gray white),

Yarn tension rating: 4, 4, Background colour: black.

5. Conclusions

Fabric simulation technology research is a subject involving many aspects of knowledge and technology research and application. On the one hand, it needs to jacquard theoretical knowledge with practice. On the other hand; it also needs to screen and apply various technologies, which belongs to a deeper research topic. Finally the corresponding simulation system is developed by using the computer programming language VC++ 6.0 and HZCAD the computer simulation of this kind of fabric is realized and some simulation results are obtained. This research provide some ideas for the computer simulation of other types of jacquard warp knitted fabrics; even ordinary high-speed warp knitted fabrics, and provide some reference value for the follow-up development and improvement of the CAD system of this kind of fabrics. It is hoped that the successors can further study the subject and improve the simulation algorithm, especially to optimize the yarn simulation model for warp knitted fabrics, and further consider the influence of the deformation of the loop structure in the fabrics, so as to develop the simulation algorithm. The simulation system of loop-shaped jacquard warp knitted fabrics has realistic simulation effect.

Acknowledgements

This research was successfully completed under the encouragement and careful guidance of Professor Dr. Zhongmin Deng. The instructor's profound knowledge, conscientious academic attitude, realistic research style, and self-denying work spirit have made me deeply

moved and unforgettable, and set an example for me to learn. During the study, whether it was in study or in life, the tutor gave me great help and selfless care. I got the training, improved my professional level of warp knitting and computer programming skills and laid the research for my later research.

References

- [1] Han Ling, Duan Yafeng, Textile CAD/CAM Status Analysis, Hebei Textile, 2002, (2): 11.
- [2] Atanasova R. and Petrov Kh., Comparative analysis of some CAD/CAM systems for the design of garments (Bulgarian), Tekstil I Obleklo 2002, 2002, (9): 49 (53).
- [3] Ren Ying, Zhang Ruiyun, Development and Trend of Textile CAD at Home and Abroad, Journal of Textile Science, 1999, 20 (6): 382 (385).
- [4] Wu Yili, Yan Gangfeng, Exploration of Computer simulation Display Method for Fabrics, Journal of Textile Science, 1999, 20 (5): 36 (38).
- [5] Jia Zhiguo, Wang Xuejun, Wang Dehuang, Development of Fabric simulation Software, Journal of Dalian Institute of Light Industry, 2004, 23 (4): 30 (32).
- [6] Jiang Gaoming, Zong Lisheng, Modern Warp Knitting Technology and Equipment, China Textile Publishing House, 2001.
- [7] Jiang Gaoming, RSJ4/1 Warp Knitting Machine Structural Principle and Jacquard Method, Knitting Industry, 2003 (5): 54 (56).
- [8] Cong Honglian, RSJ4/1 Jacquard Machine Pattern Design Approach, Shanghai Textile Technology, 2003, (5): 29 31.
- [9] Guping, The mathematical model for fabrics weave design and its applications, Journal – of Suzhou-Silk-Textile-Technology, 1995, 15 (1): 14 (23).
- [10] Jiang Gaoming, Research on CAD Theory of Jacquard Warp Knitted Fabrics, Knitting Industry, 2002, (6): 27 (28).

© 2019 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA . Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

